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New record of *Carpomya wiedemanni* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Ukraine

L. Ilminska^{1*}, V. Korneyev^{2,3**}

¹Independent citizen scientist, 20141 Dzendzelivka, Cherkasy Region, Ukraine

²I.I.Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology NAS of Ukraine, vul. Bohdana Khmelnytskogo, 15, Kyiv, 01054 Ukraine

³Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Invalidenstr. 43, 10115 Berlin, Germany

E-mails: * lubava.dzen@gmail.com, ** valery.korneyev@gmail.com

Carpomya (Goniglossum) wiedemanni (Meigen, 1826) is a peculiar fruit fly species found throughout southern and central Europe (Austria, Belgium, Germany, France (mainland and Corsica), Great Britain, Hungary, Italy (mainland and Sicily), The Netherlands, south-western Russia, Spain (mainland), Switzerland, and Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2013) to Armenia (Korneyev et al. 2018). The second species (or subspecies), *C. (G.) liat* (Freidberg) is restricted to south-eastern Turkey and Israel (Freidberg, 2016).

It has been recorded from Ukraine on the basis of specimens collected by Jaroszewski (1877) in Kharkiv and Myrhorod (Poltava region) in the second half of the 19th century, but its identification needs to be confirmed, and no material has been found either in St. Petersburg or in Kharkiv collections. Another specimen from Crimea (Kerch Peninsula, Opuk Mt., 45.03 N, 36.22 E, slopes, 21.06.1950, I. Maltsev leg.) was collected more than 70 years ago and not in the mainland part of Ukraine.

Larvae of *C. wiedemanni* live in the fleshy fruits of *Bryonia alba* L. and *B. dioica* Jacq. (Cucurbitaceae) (Silvestri, 1920), herbaceous perennial vines that are occasionally occurring in Western Europe and Ukraine. In recent decades, *Bryonia alba* and *B. dioica* have been used as ornamental climbers on fences and have become noxious weeds in North America (Kujawska & Svanberg, 2019).

In Berlin and Frankfurt (Main), *B. dioica* is a common ruderal plant, the fruits of which are attacked by *C. wiedemanni* larvae in practically all the localities examined here (V. Korneyev, unpublished data).

In Ukraine, an adult male of *C. wiedemanni* was observed by the 1st author (LI) on 09.06.2024: Cherkasy region, Uman district, Dzendzelivka (48.9746 N, 30.3636 E) on flowering *Bryonia alba* (Fig.1).

This is the first confirmed record of *C. wiedemanni* in the mainland Ukraine since Jaroszewski (1877). The latter record was considered unconfirmed and doubtful for almost 150 years.

Fig. 1. *Carpomya (Goniglossum) wiedemanni*, adult flies on *Bryonia alba* plant in Cherkasy Region. Photo by L. Ilminska.

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